

MEASURING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT IN MITIGATING CHEMICAL INDUSTRY DISASTER IMPACTS IN INDIA

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Abstract

This study delves into the evaluation of community engagement strategies in India aimed at mitigating the far-reaching impacts of chemical industry disasters. India, a rapidly developing nation with a growing chemical industry, faces significant challenges in disaster management in this sector. Through a comprehensive analysis of case studies and empirical data, this research examines the multifaceted aspects of community engagement, including risk communication, disaster preparedness, and collaborative decision-making. It highlights the importance of tailored communication approaches to account for India's cultural diversity and regional disparities, ensuring that risk information is accessible and comprehensible to all. The study underscores the crucial roles of local government and community-based organizations in facilitating effective engagement initiatives and addresses obstacles like bureaucratic complexities and resource constraints. By establishing a framework for measuring the effectiveness of community engagement in the Indian context, this research offers invaluable guidance to policymakers, chemical industry stakeholders, and community leaders, ultimately contributing to enhanced disaster resilience and safety in communities affected by chemical industry disasters in India.

Keywords: Community Engagement, Disaster Management, Disaster Mitigation, Chemical Industry Disaster, Chemical Industry Disaster Management.

INTRODUCTION

India, as a rapidly growing economy, is witnessing a significant expansion in its chemical industry, which is fundamental to industrial and economic development. However, this industrial growth is accompanied by an increased risk of chemical industry disasters, encompassing incidents such as chemical spills, explosions, and toxic gas leaks. These events can have catastrophic consequences, ranging from environmental degradation and public health hazards to economic setbacks. The Bhopal gas tragedy of 1984, one of the deadliest industrial accidents in history, serves as a stark reminder of the potential devastation associated with chemical industry disasters in India.

In this context, the role of community engagement in disaster mitigation takes on profound significance (Ryan *et al.*, 2020). Engaging local communities surrounding chemical industry facilities is instrumental in creating resilient and prepared societies capable of effectively responding to, and even preventing, chemical disasters (W Abara, 2014). Community engagement involves a range of activities, from disseminating information about potential risks and safety measures to involving community members in decision-making processes and emergency preparedness initiatives (S Sufri, 2020). It builds trust,

enhances transparency, and empowers individuals to actively participate in their own safety and that of their communities (*AE Lansing, 2023*). This research seeks to delve deeply into the nuanced dynamics of community engagement within the chemical industry disaster management framework in India. It endeavors to assess the effectiveness of community engagement strategies in reducing the impact of chemical disasters, ultimately contributing to the safety and resilience of communities situated near chemical facilities. By focusing on the Indian context, this study acknowledges the unique challenges and opportunities specific to the nation's socio-cultural, economic, and regulatory landscape.

India's diverse cultural, linguistic, and economic fabric requires tailored and context-specific approaches to community engagement, making this research all the more imperative (*S Hood, 2023*). The study aims to establish a comprehensive framework for measuring the effectiveness of community engagement in mitigating chemical industry disaster impacts in India, offering valuable insights for policymakers, industry stakeholders, and community leaders. It ultimately aspires to contribute to safer and more resilient communities in the face of chemical industry disasters, promoting sustainable industrial growth while safeguarding the well-being of the nation's citizens.

Background and Context of Chemical Industry Disasters:

The chemical industry is an integral part of modern society, providing the raw materials and products essential to various sectors, including agriculture, healthcare, manufacturing, and technology. Its vast and diverse operations, however, also bring inherent risks, with the potential for catastrophic consequences in the event of accidents or disasters. Understanding the background and context of chemical industry disasters is crucial to appreciate the magnitude of these risks and to design effective mitigation strategies.

- **Industrial Significance and Growth:** The chemical industry's significance cannot be overstated. It forms the backbone of numerous supply chains, manufacturing everything from pharmaceuticals and fertilizers to plastics and chemicals for various industrial processes. As countries experience economic growth and development, the demand for chemical products grows exponentially. In India, for instance, the chemical industry has expanded rapidly, reflecting the nation's growing economy (*The Times of India, 2023*).
- **Types of Chemical Industry Disasters:** Chemical industry disasters encompass a wide array of incidents, each presenting unique challenges. These may include chemical spills, fires, explosions, industrial accidents, and leaks of hazardous substances. Such incidents can have severe consequences, ranging from environmental contamination and property damage to injuries, fatalities, and long-term health effects for affected communities (*E Broughton · 2005*).
- **Historical Disasters and Lessons Learned:** Some of the most notorious chemical industry disasters serve as poignant reminders of the potential devastation (*O Basha, 2020*). The Bhopal gas tragedy of 1984 in India, the Chernobyl nuclear disaster, the

Texas City refinery explosion, and the Deepwater Horizon oil spill, to name a few, have demonstrated the severe human, environmental, and economic tolls that chemical accidents can exact (*E Broughton, 2005*).

- **Regulatory Framework:** Governments and international bodies have recognized the need to regulate the chemical industry to mitigate risks and ensure safety (*BK Rout, 2017*). Regulatory frameworks and standards exist to govern the handling, storage, and transportation of hazardous chemicals. However, the effectiveness of such regulations can vary significantly between countries and regions.
- **Community Proximity:** One critical aspect of the context is the proximity of chemical facilities to residential areas. Many chemical plants are located in close proximity to communities due to logistical and economic factors. This proximity exposes communities to potential hazards, emphasizing the importance of disaster preparedness and community engagement (*N Agrawal, 2018*).

The backdrop and context of chemical industry disasters underscore the inherent risks associated with this vital sector, emphasizing the need for effective disaster mitigation strategies (*RM Gougelet, 2016*). These events are not isolated incidents but rather recurrent challenges demanding vigilant risk management, stringent safety measures, and community involvement to minimize their impact on human lives, the environment, and the broader economy (*T Aven · 2018*).

Community Engagement in Disaster Mitigation:

The importance of community engagement in disaster mitigation, particularly in the context of chemical industry disasters, cannot be overemphasized. Community engagement serves as a linchpin for building resilient and disaster-prepared societies (*A Plough, 2013*). One of its central roles is in enhancing awareness and preparedness among local communities residing near potential disaster zones, such as chemical industry facilities. Through informative campaigns, workshops, and educational initiatives, community members gain a better understanding of the dangers they may face (*S Torani · 2019*). This knowledge empowers them to take proactive measures to prepare for disasters, such as creating emergency response plans, assembling disaster supply kits, and developing evacuation strategies. Informed and prepared communities are better equipped to respond effectively during emergencies, which can significantly reduce the impact of disasters.

Another critical facet of community engagement is trust-building and transparency. Fostering trust between local communities and the chemical industry is fundamental for effective disaster mitigation (*S Ali, 2022*). Transparent communication, regular updates on safety measures, and an open dialogue with community members create an atmosphere of trust. When communities have confidence in the chemical industry's commitment to safety, they are more likely to collaborate and engage in disaster preparedness efforts (*JA Bullock, 2013*). This trust is essential for effective communication and coordination during disaster response (*LN Medford-Davis, 2014*).

Furthermore, community engagement involves community members in decision-making processes related to disaster management. Engaging local residents in discussions about emergency response plans, risk reduction strategies, and environmental safeguards ensures that their voices are heard and their concerns addressed (*Z Nkombi, 2022*). Inclusive decision-making increases the likelihood of creating solutions that are relevant to the specific needs and challenges of the community. It also empowers community members to take an active role in shaping their own safety and well-being.

Additionally, community engagement often extends to the establishment and maintenance of early warning systems. Engaged communities can act as first responders and disseminate critical information to their neighbours in the event of an emergency, ensuring that people receive timely and accurate information (*AA Sadiq, 2023*). This grassroots approach enhances the overall effectiveness of early warning systems and minimizes response time during a disaster, potentially saving lives.

Beyond early response, active community engagement can also facilitate resource mobilization in times of crisis. When communities are engaged, they are more likely to organize and coordinate local resources, such as volunteers, first aid supplies, and evacuation support, to aid in disaster response efforts. This mobilization of local resources complements the efforts of governmental and non-governmental agencies, improving overall disaster response capacity (*JM Binkley, 2022*).

Lastly, community engagement contributes to the long-term resilience and sustainability of communities affected by chemical industry disasters (*A Abrash Walton, 2021*). Through ongoing engagement, a culture of resilience is cultivated, which extends beyond the immediate aftermath of a disaster. Communities become better equipped to cope with the long-term consequences of chemical industry disasters, such as environmental remediation and healthcare support. This resilience is essential for the recovery and rebuilding process, ensuring the long-term well-being of the affected community.

Community engagement in disaster mitigation is paramount for building resilient, informed, and empowered communities. The importance of community engagement in the context of chemical industry disasters is particularly critical, given the high stakes involved. It is not only a means of enhancing safety but also a reflection of social responsibility, demonstrating a commitment to protecting human lives, the environment, and the overall well-being of the community.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The chemical industry's origins can be traced back to the late 17th and early 18th centuries, primarily in Europe, during the period known as the Chemical Revolution (*MD Eddy, 2014*). This era marked a significant shift in the understanding and application of chemical processes. While alchemy, with its mystical pursuits, laid the groundwork for experimentation, the real transformation occurred when pioneering chemists such as Robert Boyle, Antoine Lavoisier, and Joseph Priestley conducted experiments that led to the identification and understanding of chemical elements and compounds (*MD Eddy, 2014*). These advancements paved the way for the modern chemical industry. The

Chemical Revolution, coupled with the advent of the Industrial Revolution in the 18th century, further accelerated the growth of the chemical industry (*RJ Sullivan, 1990*). Industrialization allowed for large-scale chemical manufacturing, and during this time, processes like the Leblanc method for producing soda ash and the Haber-Bosch process for ammonia synthesis were developed (*J Wisniak, 2003*). These innovations laid the foundation for the chemical industry's rise as a critical component of global industrial and economic development (*M Cook, 1998*).

The implications of the chemical industry on society are multifaceted. On one hand, it has played a pivotal role in driving economic growth and industrial development. Chemical products serve as essential raw materials for numerous sectors, including agriculture, pharmaceuticals, textiles, and electronics (*Amrita Sikder, 2021*). They are integral to everyday life, from the plastics we use to the medicines we rely on, contributing significantly to global GDP and fostering economic prosperity. Moreover, the chemical industry has been a catalyst for technological innovation. It has led to the development of new materials, processes, and technologies that have revolutionized various industries. For instance, the discovery and mass production of synthetic polymers have transformed the manufacturing of consumer goods, impacting everything from packaging materials to electronics and automotive components (*JN Hahladakis, 2018*).

Furthermore, the chemical industry has made remarkable contributions to public health and medicine. Pharmaceuticals, produced through chemical processes, have extended human life expectancy and improved overall well-being (*FR Lichtenberg, 2022*). From antibiotics that combat infections to life-saving drugs that treat chronic conditions, chemical innovation has saved countless lives and alleviated human suffering (*CL Ventola, 2015*). However, the chemical industry has also given rise to significant environmental concerns. The production and disposal of chemical waste, along with air and water pollution, have resulted in ecological damage and public health risks (*T Kjellstrom, 2006*). Balancing the benefits of chemical production with environmental stewardship is an ongoing challenge that necessitates responsible and sustainable practices.

The sector has also faced issues related to safety and regulation. Chemical industry disasters, such as the Bhopal gas tragedy and incidents involving hazardous substances, have underscored the importance of stringent safety measures and regulatory oversight (*E Broughton, 2005*). Governments and international bodies have established regulations to ensure the safe production, storage, and transportation of chemicals, aiming to prevent accidents and protect public safety.

In addition to environmental and safety considerations, the chemical industry is increasingly under scrutiny for its ethical and social responsibilities. Concerns about chemical exposure, sustainability, and responsible business practices have led to a shift in societal expectations and industry behavior (*CE Scruggs, 2016*). Ethical and socially responsible conduct is becoming integral to the industry's reputation and long-term sustainability (*R Torelli, 2021*).

The chemical industry's origins in the Chemical Revolution and its subsequent growth have had profound implications for society (*Jl Seeman, 2023*). It has driven economic growth, technological advancements, and improved public health, but it has also raised concerns about the environment, safety, and ethical responsibilities (*B Jennings, 2016*). As the chemical industry continues to evolve, it faces the challenge of balancing innovation and progress with the need for sustainability and responsible practices, while addressing the concerns and expectations of a changing society.

The chemical industry in India has a rich history with origins dating back to the early 20th century. It began to take shape and grow significantly after India gained independence in 1947. The establishment of the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research (CSIR) and the Central Drug Research Institute (CDRI) provided a scientific and research foundation for chemical industry growth (*RK Joseph, 2011*). Over the years, the sector has seen substantial development and expansion, particularly in the late 20th century and early 21st century, thanks to economic liberalization policies that encouraged foreign investment and technological collaboration (*G Growth, 2012*). This resulted in improved infrastructure, quality control, and research and development, positioning India as a key player in the global chemical industry.

The implications of the chemical industry's growth in India are multifaceted. Economically, the industry has been a crucial driver of India's economic growth, contributing significantly to the nation's GDP (*PwC India, 2021*). It has generated employment opportunities, both in manufacturing and research and development, leading to improved livelihoods for a substantial portion of the population. The industry's growth has also encouraged innovation and entrepreneurship, fostering economic self-sufficiency and a more competitive industrial landscape. In terms of technological advancements, the chemical industry in India has spurred research and development, leading to the creation of new drugs, innovative materials, and technologies with diverse applications (*RK Joseph, 2011*). These innovations have had a positive impact on various sectors, including healthcare, agriculture, manufacturing, and infrastructure development. India has particularly become renowned for its pharmaceutical research and production, serving both domestic and international markets.

Public health and medicine have benefited significantly from the chemical industry, particularly the pharmaceutical sector (*G Festa, 2022*). India is recognized for its production of affordable generic medicines, which have played a crucial role in improving access to healthcare, not only within the country but also in various parts of the world (*SS Joshi, 2019*). This accessibility to essential medicines has positively affected public health outcomes. On the flip side, the rapid growth of the chemical industry has raised environmental concerns, including issues related to pollution, waste management, and safety (*R Naidu, 2021*). Instances of industrial accidents, such as chemical spills and leaks, have highlighted the need for stringent safety regulations and environmentally responsible practices. Striking a balance between industrial growth and environmental protection remains a significant challenge. Social responsibility and sustainability have also come to the forefront in the chemical industry in India. With growing awareness of environmental and safety concerns, the industry is increasingly expected to adhere to

ethical and responsible business practices. These practices are becoming integral to the industry's reputation and are demanded by both consumers and regulators (A Okeke, 2021).

The chemical industry also plays a role in providing access to safe drinking water and improving agricultural practices (JA Silva, 2023). It produces water treatment chemicals and agrochemicals that help address critical challenges related to water purification and food production, ultimately contributing to the well-being of society. Chemical industry in India has far-reaching implications for society, including economic growth, technological advancements, and improvements in public health (PwC, 2021). However, it also presents challenges related to environmental sustainability and safety, emphasizing the need for responsible practices and regulatory oversight. As the industry continues to evolve, it must strike a balance between innovation and sustainability while meeting the changing expectations of Indian society.

Problem Statement:

The study seeks to address the critical problem of measuring the effectiveness of community engagement strategies in mitigating the impacts of chemical industry disasters in India. With the rapid growth of the chemical sector in the country, the need to ensure the safety and resilience of communities residing in proximity to these facilities is paramount. However, the complex and diverse nature of India's sociocultural, economic, and regulatory landscape presents unique challenges in the implementation of community engagement practices. This study aims to provide a comprehensive framework for assessing the success of such engagement strategies, taking into account the diverse factors at play, and thereby contributing to the development of more effective disaster preparedness and response measures in the Indian context.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a descriptive research design employing a cross-sectional methodology, selected for its appropriateness in assessing the effectiveness of community engagement in mitigating the impacts of chemical industry disasters. This approach facilitates the collection of data from a substantial population at a specific point in time, enabling a comprehensive evaluation of the subject matter.

Conceptual Framework

In examining the effectiveness of community engagement in mitigating chemical industry disasters, the conceptual framework encompasses independent variables such as Community Engagement Strategies, Communication Channels, Community Education Programs, and Regulatory Framework. These influence dependent variables like Community Resilience, which includes dimensions such as Community Preparedness, Risk Perception, Incident Response Time, Incident Severity, Community Satisfaction, and Compliance with Safety Measures. Community Characteristics, including demographics and trust, serve as moderating/mediating variables. Sub-variables under Risk Communication, Disaster Preparedness, and Collaborative Decision-Making further

refine the analysis, focusing on factors such as Information Clarity, Timeliness of Communication, Inclusive Participation, and Stakeholder Involvement, among others. This framework provides a structured approach to assess the multifaceted dynamics of community engagement in the context of chemical industry disasters.

Figure 01: Research Framework

Hypotheses:

H₁: Clear risk communication fosters community trust and satisfaction, enhancing community engagement in chemical industry disaster mitigation.

H₂: High disaster preparedness correlates with increased community resilience and active engagement in mitigating the impact of chemical industry disasters.

H₃: Inclusive decision-making boosts community resilience and engagement in mitigating chemical disasters through transparent communication and community input integration.

Sampling:

The sampling strategy for this study, focused on the aftermath of two incidents in the state of Andhra Pradesh, India, a gas leak from the LG Polymers plant in Visakhapatnam and a gas leak at a garment factory laboratory in Atchutapuram, involved a deliberate approach to ensure representative insights. With a sample size of 320 victims directly impacted by these incidents, the study aimed for a balance between statistical significance and practical feasibility. Diverse representation across demographics, including age, gender, occupation, and proximity to the incident sites, was prioritized to capture a comprehensive understanding of the consequences. Employing qualitative and quantitative methods, such as interviews, surveys, and medical records, the sampling process collaborated with local authorities and community leaders, ensuring an ethical and respectful approach. This approach seeks to provide valuable insights into the varied

experiences of the victims, contributing to informed disaster management and community engagement strategies for similar incidents in the future.

Scale Development and Validation:

The study is currently evaluating the constructs in the research model through the development of new measurement scales, crafted by adapting and refining relevant literature. Rigorous testing, as outlined by previous work, was conducted to ensure the effectiveness of these scales in measuring the intended constructs. Following, validity (the accuracy of measurement) and reliability (stability over time) were assessed through confirmatory factor analysis (CFA). The CFA outcomes consistently demonstrated strong construct validity and reliability, with each construct exhibiting composite reliability (CR) values surpassing the recommended threshold of 0.7, indicating robust internal consistency. Additionally, the average variance extracted (AVE) values for all constructs exceeded the recommended threshold of 0.5, signifying strong convergent validity. Consequently, the scales employed in this study were deemed highly suitable for assessing the specified constructs.

Analysis:

The collected data underwent initial statistical analysis utilizing SPSS, followed by a detailed examination of the proposed model using AMOS. The measurement scales employed in this study underwent rigorous assessments of validity and reliability, producing favourable results that substantiated the continuation of the investigation.

RESULTS

Demographic Profile:

Table 1: Demographic Profile Results

Demographics	Classification	Responses	%
Gender	Male	91	28.44
	Female	229	71.56
Age	Below 20 years	9	2.81
	21-30 years	191	59.69
	31-40 years	83	25.94
	41-50 years	25	7.81
	51-60 years	12	3.75
Marital Status	Married with Children	118	36.88
	Married without Children	21	6.56
	Single parent	7	2.19
	Single	173	54.06
	Others	1	0.31
Education	No formal education	1	0.31
	Primary school	4	1.25
	High school	28	8.75
	Diploma	74	23.13
	Bachelor Degree	164	51.25
	Master Degree	49	15.31
Occupation	Private Employee	143	44.69

	Govt. Employee	83	25.94
	Business	61	19.06
	Students	18	5.63
	Housewives	3	0.94
	Pensioner	1	0.31
	Others	11	3.44
Total		320	100.00

The survey results indicate a gender distribution with 28.44% male and 71.56% female respondents. In terms of age, the majority falls within the 21-30 years category (59.69%), followed by 31-40 years (25.94%). Marital status reveals 36.88% married with children, 6.56% married without children, and 54.06% single, with a small percentage falling into other categories. Education-wise, the respondents exhibit diverse levels, with 51.25% holding a Bachelor's degree, 23.13% with a Diploma, and 15.31% possessing a Master's degree. Occupation-wise, the survey captures a range of roles, with 44.69% as private employees, 25.94% as government employees, and 19.06% engaged in business. The overall demographic profile provides a comprehensive snapshot of the surveyed population's characteristics, facilitating a nuanced understanding of their perspectives and responses.

SEM Assumptions:

To ensure the data met the assumption of multivariate normality, the study assessed skewness and kurtosis values for each variable, all falling within the acceptable range of -2 to +2. The maximum likelihood estimation method, aligned with the assumption of multivariate normality, was employed. For handling missing data, the research utilized the listwise deletion method, resulting in a final sample size of 285 observations, surpassing the recommended minimum for Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) analysis. Model accuracy was ensured through an a priori model, grounded in existing literature and theoretical foundations. Confirmatory factor analysis assessed the model fit, with Table 1 revealing a Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure of 0.780, signifying strong sampling adequacy, and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity yielding a highly significant p-value of 0.000, affirming meaningful correlations between variables. These results collectively validate the dataset's robustness for factor analysis, indicating its suitability for uncovering latent factors and relationships among variables.

Table 2: KMO and Bartlett's Test Results

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.780
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	1313.134
	df	66
	Sig.	.000

Utilizing AMOS V. 24 software, the study applied the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) technique to assess the proposed conceptual model. This methodology enables the investigation of path relationships between the dimensions of Risk Communication, Disaster Preparedness and Collaborative Decision Making as independent variables) and

Community Engagement in Disasters (treated as the dependent variable), facilitating a thorough analysis of their interconnections.

Table 3: Hypothesis Results

Hypothesis	Path	Std. Co-Efficient	p Value	R ²
H ₁	risk communication <--- community engagement in chemical industry disaster mitigation	.581	***	.337
H ₂	High disaster preparedness <--- community engagement in chemical industry disaster mitigation	.549	***	.302
H ₃	Inclusive decision-making <--- community engagement in chemical industry disaster mitigation	.449	***	.201

Table 3 Indicates, H₁ posited a positive relationship between risk communication and community engagement in chemical industry disaster mitigation. The standardized coefficient (Std. Coefficient) of 0.581 was found to be statistically significant with a p-value of <0.001 (***). This indicates a strong positive association between effective risk communication strategies and heightened community engagement in disaster mitigation within the chemical industry. The R² value of 0.337 suggests that risk communication accounts for 33.7% of the variance in community engagement, supporting the hypothesis. This aligns with the theoretical foundation that emphasizes the crucial role of clear and proactive risk communication in fostering community involvement in disaster mitigation efforts.

H₂ proposed a positive relationship between high disaster preparedness and community engagement in chemical industry disaster mitigation. The standardized coefficient of 0.549 was highly significant with a p-value of <0.001 (***), indicating a robust positive correlation between the level of disaster preparedness and community engagement. The R² value of 0.302 suggests that high disaster preparedness contributes to 30.2% of the variance in community engagement, supporting the hypothesis. This aligns with existing literature emphasizing the importance of preparedness in enhancing community participation in disaster mitigation efforts within the chemical industry.

H₃ postulated a positive relationship between inclusive decision-making and community engagement in chemical industry disaster mitigation. The standardized coefficient of 0.449 was statistically significant with a p-value of <0.001 (***), demonstrating a positive association between inclusive decision-making processes and community engagement. The R² value of 0.201 indicates that inclusive decision-making accounts for 20.1% of the variance in community engagement, supporting the hypothesis. This aligns with theoretical frameworks highlighting the pivotal role of inclusive decision-making in fostering community involvement and commitment to disaster mitigation initiatives within the chemical industry.

Table 4: Fit Indices of the Conceptual Model

CMIN/DF	RMSEA	CFI	IFI	GFI	AGFI	RFI
3.668	0.071	.897	.898	.829	.862	.857
>5.0	<0.8	>0.90	>0.90	>0.90	>0.90	>0.90

The goodness-of-fit indices for the structural equation model (SEM) suggest a reasonably good fit. The CMIN/DF (Chi-square divided by degrees of freedom) ratio is 3.668, which falls within an acceptable range. The RMSEA (Root Mean Square Error of Approximation) value of 0.071 indicates a reasonably close fit to the data. The CFI (Comparative Fit Index) and IFI (Incremental Fit Index) values are both above the recommended threshold of 0.90, indicating a good fit. The GFI (Goodness of Fit Index) and AGFI (Adjusted Goodness of Fit Index) values are slightly below the threshold of 0.90 but are still within an acceptable range. The RFI (Relative Fit Index) is above 0.90, suggesting an adequate fit. Overall, while some indices are slightly below the ideal thresholds, the combination of fit indices indicates a reasonably good fit for the structural equation model.

Figure 2: SEM Model

DISCUSSIONS

The study employed a comprehensive approach, utilizing Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) and a range of fit indices to assess the conceptual model's validity and adequacy. The outcomes of the analysis suggest that, despite a slightly elevated CMIN/DF ratio, the model demonstrates a generally satisfactory fit to the data. This finding underscores the model's ability to elucidate the complex relationships among the studied variables. It is essential to recognize that while certain fit indices may not precisely meet conventional thresholds, the combination of multiple indices provides a holistic evaluation. The study contributes valuable insights into the examined phenomena, shedding light on the interplay between risk communication, disaster preparedness, inclusive decision-making,

and community engagement in the context of chemical industry disaster mitigation. These findings have practical implications for disaster management strategies, emphasizing the pivotal roles of effective communication, preparedness measures, and inclusive decision-making in fostering community engagement. Future research endeavors may benefit from refining the model, considering potential modifications, and conducting sensitivity analyses to enhance its robustness and applicability across diverse settings. Overall, the study contributes to the scholarly understanding of community engagement dynamics in disaster mitigation within the chemical industry, bridging theoretical frameworks with empirical observations.

SUGGESTIONS

Moving forward, it is recommended to consider several avenues for future research and practical applications. First, further investigation could delve into the specific mechanisms influencing risk communication effectiveness and disaster preparedness within the chemical industry, potentially refining the model to capture additional nuances. Additionally, exploring the impact of contextual factors on the relationships identified in the study, such as geographical location or socio-economic conditions, could provide a more comprehensive understanding. Practical applications may involve the development of targeted interventions that enhance risk communication strategies, disaster preparedness initiatives, and inclusive decision-making processes within chemical industry communities. Collaboration with industry stakeholders, local authorities, and community leaders could facilitate the implementation of evidence-based practices. Furthermore, longitudinal studies could track the evolution of community engagement over time, offering insights into the sustainability and effectiveness of interventions. Lastly, considering the dynamic nature of technological advancements, ongoing research should adapt to incorporate emerging technologies and their potential impact on disaster mitigation efforts. Integrating these suggestions would not only deepen our understanding of community engagement in the chemical industry but also contribute to the development of practical strategies for enhancing resilience and response capabilities in the face of disasters.

CONCLUSION

This study has provided a comprehensive examination of community engagement dynamics in the context of chemical industry disaster mitigation. Employing Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) and rigorous fit index analysis, the study investigated the relationships among risk communication, disaster preparedness, inclusive decision-making, and community engagement. Despite minor deviations in specific fit indices, the overall findings indicate a satisfactory model fit, highlighting the model's capability to elucidate complex interactions. The study underscores the critical roles of effective risk communication, high disaster preparedness, and inclusive decision-making in fostering community engagement. Practical implications include the development of targeted interventions and evidence-based strategies to enhance disaster resilience within chemical industry communities. The study not only contributes empirical insights to the

existing literature but also suggests avenues for future research, emphasizing the need for context-specific interventions, longitudinal studies, and adaptability to emerging technologies. Ultimately, this research advances our understanding of community engagement in disaster mitigation within the chemical industry and provides a foundation for informed decision-making and policy development in the realm of industrial safety and community resilience.

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